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OVERALL EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE (OE) AND ADJUSTMENT OF ADOLESCENT GIRLS

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Abstract

India's, Emotional Intelligence has of recent been suggested as a critical factor in adjustment to life in general and to work and work performance in particular (Goleman, 1995; 1998).The present study aims to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and adjustment. For this purpose a randomly selected sample of 60 adolescent females (age group between 18-21 yrs) enrolled for different undergraduate programmes from Mumbai were selected. The study is a correlational one in which emotional intelligence stands as independent variable & adjustment as dependent variable. Emotional Intelligence Inventory by Dr. S.K.Mangal and Adjustment Inventory for College Students by Singh and Sinha were administered to the total sample.The scores were subjected to Pearson Product Moment Correlation and further Regression analysis was done using SPSS (version 19).The results obtained indicated significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Adjustment.

Key Words: *Emotional Intelligence, Adjustment, Adolescent Females*

Introduction

Emotional Intelligence refers to the emotional information as it relates to the perception, assimilation, expression, regulation & management (Mayer, et al., 2000).It is believed to encompass social and cognitive functions related to the expression of emotion (Schuttle, et. al. 1998).

Many people are extraordinarily talented, conceptually brilliant and have a very high IQ. They excel in computers, science and mathematics. Sadly though, they are not particularly likable people. Many of them are aggressive and brutal in their responses to the outside world. They have little or no feelings for people around them. They feel psychologically awkward in relationships, have no social graces or even a social or personal life. Such negative traits are fatal handicaps even for high IQ managers with sound technical knowledge (Singh, D., 2001).

Emotional Intelligence constitutes 3 psychological dimensions: emotional sensitivity, emotional maturity and emotional competency, which motivate an individual to recognize truthfully, interpret honestly and handle tactfully the dynamics of human behavior. Your emotional makeup is the product of your learning experiences. Emotional competencies, abilities and concepts are learned through role models, i.e. teachers, parents, celluloid heroes and so on. You learn emotional intelligence through the social learning process. Almost all over the world, most children spend 10-15 years of their life learning to develop their academic skills. In the process emotions are either completely or largely ignored and there is no effort to inculcate them in our personal and professional life.

People with low emotional intelligence experience feeling of general unhappiness. They end up with decisions which may not make them feel 'good', because they are not aware of their own inner emotion. Whereas people with high emotional intelligence experience feeling of general happiness. They are more likely to recognize the source of their emotions, and have the confidence to take appropriate actions, thus increasing long-term happiness.

Adjustment involves the gratification of a person's needs as governed by the demands of various environmental situations. This is not, however, a one-way process: an individual maintains the balance between himself and his surroundings either by modifying his own behavior or by modifying the environment. In this context, as Arkoff (1968) states: Adjustment is the interaction between a person and his environment. How one adjusts in a particular situation depends upon one's personal characteristics as the circumstances of the situation. In other words, both personal and environmental factors work side by side in adjustment. An individual is adjusted if he is adjusted to himself and to his environment

A well-adjusted person is supposed to possess the following characteristics: *Awareness of his own strengths and limitations*. A well adjusted person knows his own strengths and weaknesses. He tries to make capital out of his assets in some areas by accepting his limitations in others. *Respecting himself and others*. The dislike for one-self is a typical symptom of maladjustment An adjusted individual has respect for himself as well as for others. *An adequate level of aspiration*. His level of aspiration is neither too low nor too high in terms of his own strengths and abilities (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2011).

Social and cultural adjustments are similar to physiological adjustments. People strive to be comfortable in their surroundings and to have their psychological needs (such as love or affirmation) met through the social networks they inhabit. When needs arise, especially in new or changed surroundings, they impel interpersonal activity meant to satisfy those needs. In this way, people increase their familiarity and comfort with their environments, and they come to expect that their needs will be met in the future through their social networks. Ongoing difficulties in social and cultural adjustment may be accompanied by anxiety or depression (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2011.).

However, emotional development starts early in life & process of developing emotional quotient is not too difficult. If one can practice this early in life he can become a well adjusted & successful individual.

Method:

Sample: The sample consisted of randomly selected 60 adolescent females (age 18-21 yrs), enrolled for various undergraduate programme from Mumbai.

Tools: Following tools were used to collect relevant data in the present study.

1. The Emotional Intelligence Inventory developed by Dr. S.K. Mangal was used to measure the emotional intelligence. The inventory consists of 100 questions and measures 4 dimensions of emotional intelligence viz, Intra Personal Awareness, Inter Personal Awareness, Intra Personal Management & Inter Personal Management. Each item has 2 response categories.
2. The Adjustment Inventory for College Students (AICS) developed by Singh and Sinha was used to measure adjustment level of the participants. The inventory consists of 102 questions

and measures 5 dimensions of adjustment viz, Home, Health, social, Emotional, Educational. Each item has 2 response categories.

Variables: Independent Variable: Overall Emotional Intelligence

Dependent Variable: Adjustment scores covering all 5 domains of adjustment, (home, health, social, emotional, educational).

Hypotheses:

1. Overall Emotional Intelligence (OE) will be negatively correlated with Home adjustment. *(Since high score on emotional intelligence indicates high emotional intelligence and low score on adjustment indicates better adjustment).*
2. Overall Emotional Intelligence will be negatively correlated with Health adjustment.
3. Overall Emotional Intelligence will be negatively correlated with Social adjustment.
4. Overall Emotional Intelligence will be negatively correlated with Emotional adjustment.
5. Overall Emotional Intelligence will be negatively correlated with Educational adjustment.

Procedure:

Both the inventories were administered to the adolescent females one at a time and were asked to mark the answer that was true for themselves. The respondents were assured that their responses would be kept confidential and be used for research purpose only.

Results and Discussion:

Pearson’s product moment correlation was used to study the relationship between emotional intelligence and home, health, social, emotional and educational adjustment. The following table summarizes the obtained results.

Table 1: Summary of Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation showing relationship between Emotional intelligence and Adjustment & its various domains

	Overall adjustment	Home	Health	Social	Emotional	Educational
EI	-.727**	-.345**	-.474**	-.497**	-.664**	-.589**

**p<.01

The Pearson’s product moment correlation revealed a negative correlation between OE and Home adjustment (r=-.345, p<.01). Thus, the hypothesis stating that OE will be negatively

correlated to home adjustment has been completely supported. Simple regression was carried out to study overall emotional intelligence could be a significant predictor of educational adjustment. The results of the same are displayed below.

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis with OE as the predictor and Home adjustment as the dependent variable.

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	R	R ²	β	t
Regression	68.844	1	68.844	7.813	.345 ^a	.119	-.345	-2.795
Residual	511.089	58	8.812					
Total	579.933	59						

**p<.01

Emotional Intelligence contributed 11.9% variance in Home Adjustment (F (1, 58) =7.813, p< .01). Beta weight of the variable of emotional intelligence in explaining Home Adjustment was statistically significant. (β=-0.345, t=2.795, p<.01). Thus consistent with the assumption of the present study, emotional intelligence was found to be significant predictor of home adjustment.

Now once again with reference to Table 1, it could be seen that there is a negative correlation between OE and Health adjustment (r= -.474, p<.01). Thus, supporting the 2nd hypothesis. Simple regression was carried out to study if overall emotional intelligence was significant predictor of Health adjustment. The results are displayed below.

Table 3: Summary of simple regression analysis with OE as the predictor and Health Adjustment as the dependent variable.

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	R	R ²	β	t
Regression	97.554	1	97.554	18.976	.497 ^a	.247	-.497	-4.356
Residual	298.179	58	5.141					
Total	395.733	59						

**p<.01

Emotional Intelligence contributed 24.7% variance in Health Adjustment ($F(1, 58) = 18.976, p < .01$). Beta weight of the variable of emotional intelligence in explaining Health Adjustment was statistically significant. ($\beta = -.497, t = -4.356, p < .01$). Thus consistent with the assumption of the present study, emotional intelligence was found to be significant predictor of health adjustment.

Getting back to Hypothesis no.3, with reference to table 1, it is seen that there is negative correlation between OE and social adjustment ($r = -.497, p < .01$). The hypothesis has been completely supported by the results obtained. Summary of simple regression has been displayed in the table below.

Table 4: Summary of simple regression analysis with OE as the predictor and Social Adjustment as the dependent variable.

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	R	R ²	β	t
Regression	137.915	1	137.915	16.838	.474 ^a	.225	-.474	-4.103
Residual	475.068	58	8.191					
Total	612.983	59						

** $p < .01$

Emotional Intelligence contributed 22.5% variance in Social Adjustment ($F(1, 58) = 16.838, p < .01$). Beta weight of the variable of emotional intelligence in explaining Social Adjustment was statistically significant. ($\beta = -.474, t = -4.356, p < .01$). Thus consistent with the assumption of the present study.

Again with reference to Table 1, it has revealed negative correlation between OE and Emotional adjustment ($r = -.664, p < .01$). This has again supported the Hypothesis no. 4. To find a significant relation between the two variables; scores were subjected to simple regression the summary of which is displayed below.

Table 5: Summary of simple regression analysis with OE as the predictor and Emotional Adjustment as the dependent variable.

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	R	R ²	β	t

Regression	706.604	1	706.604	45.789	.664 ^a	.441	-.664	-6.767
Residual	895.046	58	15.432					
Total	1601.650	59						

**p<.01

Emotional Intelligence contributed 44.1% variance in Emotional Adjustment (F(1,58)=45.789,p<.01). Beta weight of the variable of emotional intelligence in explaining Emotional Adjustment was statistically significant. ($\beta = -.664$, $t = -6.767$, $p < .01$). Thus consistent with the assumption of the present study, emotional intelligence was found to be significant predictor of Emotional adjustment.

With reference to Table no 1, it could be seen that there is negative correlation between OE and Educational Adjustment ($r = -.589$, $p < .01$). Thus supporting our 5th Hypothesis. Summary table for simple regression is given below.

Table 5: Summary of simple regression analysis with OE as the predictor and Educational Adjustment as the dependent variable.

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	R	R ²	β	t
Regression	337.174	1	337.174	30.777	.589 ^a	.347	-.589	-5.548
Residual	635.410	58	10.955					
Total	972.583	59						

**p<.01

Emotional Intelligence contributed 34.7% variance in Educational Adjustment (F(1,58)=30.777,p<.01). Beta weight of the variable of emotional intelligence in explaining Educational Adjustment was statistically significant. ($\beta = -.589$, $t = -5.548$, $p < .01$). Thus consistent with the assumption of the present study, emotional intelligence was found to be significant predictor of Educational adjustment.

With the above results it could be seen that a student who possesses emotional intelligence shows better adjustment, as a result of their being emotionally intelligent. According to Mayer and Cobb (2000) the current definition of emotional intelligence as defined by Mayer and Salovey and Caruso (2000) is the capacity to process emotional information accurately and

efficiently, including the capacity to perceive, assimilate, understand and manage emotion (p 165). And since this emotional intelligence test measured inter personal awareness, intra personal awareness, inter personal management and intra personal management, a student who is high in emotional intelligence is likely to possess traits like ability to understand other peoples motives, empathy, rational thinking, environmental mastery, positive relation with others and so on. This could make him more of a well adjusted individual in life and society.

The present study has also been supported by the past research evidence where Maria Chong, Habibah Elias et. al in their study on relationship between emotional intelligence and university adjustment and academic achievement showed that there is significant relationship between students' emotional intelligence & their overall adjustment (The International Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences, Vol. 4, Issue 9, p 95-106).

Conclusion:

Analysis of the findings shows that overall emotional intelligence has a significant correlation with all the five adjustment domains.

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